

The Importance of Social Competence in Teaching Foreign Languages

Linguistics

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the theoretical aspect of formation of social-cultural competence, which is necessary in teaching foreign languages. Socio-cultural competence is the ability of a communicative communicating in a foreign language to communicate effectively with other cultures, to find the right way to communicate and to choose a sophisticated speech and behavioral strategy, to acquire social sciences and skills. The foreign language learning process is a two-way activity, as well as learning a foreign language as well as mastering the capabilities of the mother tongue and its characteristics. Therefore, every course on foreign language is an intercultural cross-cultural communication point. Formation of socio-cultural competence of future professionals involves the preparation of a multinational person. A cultural-linguistic person is a person who has a culture and linguistic potential. Such a person will also be able to acquire linguistic means not only for his own culture, but also for the realization of his communicative intentions, regardless of social context. The content of teaching, of course, contains teaching culture and spiritual heritage. Next comes formation of the social-cultural competence in the process of teaching foreign languages. Implementation of socio-cultural approach to teaching foreign languages leads to the activation of students in mastering the foreign language, ie the student acquires the national culture and values of other people. In this process, the knowledge about the country where the language is studied is strengthened.

The present article explains the notion of social-cultural competence and its peculiarities of formation in the process of teaching foreign languages.

Social-cultural competence is an effective means of formation of a personality of a foreign language teacher. It brings to development of students' personal qualities such as creativity, new ideas and comprehension of communicant's psychological state, tolerance to diversity and another point of view, positive attitude to foreign culture and its bearers.[1, p. 147]

The aim of teaching a foreign language is formation of communicative competence, which includes lingual, social-cultural competence. The absence of social-cultural background knowledge will lead to incorrect communication and can't maintain communicative competence.

Being the elements of culture, languages function in the frames of a definite culture. Students, who are taught these languages, should be aware of cultural peculiarities. National-cultural competence includes specific features of speech behavior of native language speakers and elements of social-cultural context: customs, traditions, norms, rules, social conditions, rituals, country study knowledge.

All these problems are attracting more attention of researchers who point the necessity of including teaching culture into the process of teaching foreign languages. N.G. Muravyova points: "Social-cultural competence is an integrative characteristic of a person, being aware of various

social-cultural spheres and being able to communicate with different people basing on life experience”.[2]

Learning the culture of the country of a foreign language develops mutual understanding, tolerance to each other, respect to another culture, comprehension of its peculiarities in the process of communication with foreigners.[3, p. 85]

The most effective way of learning foreign language culture is living in that country, being involved into the atmosphere of culture, traditions, customs and social norms of the country of foreign language. But not all the learners have chance for it. So, we should offer the most effective ways of development of social-cultural competence outside of authentic language sphere.[4,p.7]

The development of social-cultural competence includes 4 main steps:

1. Social-cultural knowledge - materials about the country of a foreign language, its spiritual values and cultural traditions, peculiarities of national mentality;
2. Experience of communication with foreigners - choice of the style of communication, correct expression of thoughts, and correct explanation of phenomena of foreign culture;
3. Personal attitude to the facts of foreign culture - tolerance and ability to avoid social-cultural conflicts in communication with foreigners;
4. Correct usage of socially marked language units in various spheres of cultural communication, comprehension of diversity and difference of foreign culture with native one.

We see that a language is a means of transformation of cultural experience of a country and reflection of historical changes, whose language is learnt.

Social-cultural competence suggests that knowing the norms of speech behavior gives opportunity to reveal nationally marked lexics in the texts of different styles.

Formation of social-cultural competence deals with practical, developing and upbringing functions of a language. The upbringing function is the most essential as it helps to increase the feeling of patriotism and feeling of internationalism in a young learner. Learning English, we form comprehension of world culture in a person’s mentality. We compare lingual phenomena, customs, traditions, art, and way of life of people.

A.B. Minenko identifies social-cultural content of communicative competence with a) country study, б) language study, в) culture study, г) culturology.[5]

Social-cultural component in teaching a foreign language creates the basis of background knowledge about realias, tastes, customs, and traditions of the country of the learned language. All these elements are necessary in the speech act, verbal and non-verbal behavior and are included

into the content of national culture. This component has a vast potential in the dialogue of cultures and introduction with national cultures in the development of humanity culture.[6]

The requirements for communicative and competent approach require the foreign language teaching process to be socially-cultural and professional-oriented. For this purpose it is necessary to a fore mentioned ensure effective integration of linguistic, social-cultural and professional knowledge components. The linguistic component is related to language learning, phonetics, lexica, grammar skills and skills of all types of speaking activities, as well as modern communication standards in culture of the country studied in the language, communication culture, and the socio-cultural component of the outline of communications is related to the aspects of nationalism and culture . The professional component is the skills of applying the knowledge and skills related to the field of professional communication in the process of professional intercultural dialogue.

Obtaining the knowledge of the country in which the language is studied, its national capabilities, and the ability to use this information in intercultural situations, will lead to the formation of communicative competence in another language. In particular, A.A. Verbitsky and N.P.Homyakova offer the following content of specialized language teaching:

Subject aspect - it includes linguistic means (terminology, grammatical constructions and lexical means, their applicationrules); components of socio-cultural (nationalistic and linguistic) study content are in line with the specificities activenessof professional activity.

Functional aspect is the nomenclature of functional roles performed under the conditions of real professional activity, including professional communication situations and fields.

The procedural and theoretical aspect includes the level of occupation of the profession, the competence of communicative skills in the professional sphere.[7]

In teaching the language of the specialty, it is necessary to ensure that the objective aspect of the foreign language content is to select the didactic material that imparts objectivity to culture, culture and social events in order to overcome all obstacles in understanding the interlocutor's goals.

The results of the survey show that the personal interest of students in raising the level of communicative competence in foreign languages is related to the following opportunities that help them to learn a foreign language:

- successful professional activity;
- free communication with representatives of other cultures;
- obtain necessary information from professional sources on foreign sources;

- acquisition of additional knowledge.

Today's up-to-date pedagogical practice focuses on the development of inner motivation of learners, and is based on the independent, motivated, motivated approach of the student. The formation of a profession-oriented communicative competence of future foreign language teachers can be divided into the following stages:

Students' interest in socio-cultural issues, their own culture, and intensified interpersonal communication skills. It also requires the collection of local knowledge in the context of their native language and culture, as well as in the linguistic, cultural studies.

At this stage, students will be able to combine language and culture together to improve their communicative, intellectual, emotional and social activity. This process is also related to self-study, learning and critical self-reflection, the experience of intercultural co-operation, learning the characteristics of their culture and mentality.

Adapting to a cultural context. It is a process of listening comprehension and reading through the active use of foreign language information, culturally relevant information, and the ability to distinguish between national and national cultures.

Understanding Cultural Context. It is carried out in a context of contrastive analysis of values, behaviors, and communicative culture norms taken in them and in foreign cultures.

Insightful understanding of the process of intercultural dialogue and the use of didactic techniques such as communicative, interactive, projecting will help achieve the goal of teaching a foreign language.

Formation of socio-cultural competence is achieved not only in a systematic way, but also as a means of communication, communication in the process of interpersonal and professional interaction. The main purpose of education is to study the culture of foreign countries through the language acquired in educational, developmental and educational aspects. This method is based on the individual and psychological characteristics of the students, and the functional approach to choosing the teaching material for problem assignments.

Socio-cultural competence helps to ensure the integration of the cultural and linguistic identity of the person into the system of national cultures through the formation of the cultural identity of the speakers, their traditions, standards, beliefs and the ability to use them as a representative of another culture in the process of preserving their own culture. A cultural-linguistic person is a person who has a culture and linguistic potential. Such a person will also be able to acquire linguistic means not only for his own culture, but also for the realization of his communicative intentions, regardless of social context.

Foreign language learning is a two-dimensional one, while the student learning a foreign language, as well as the capabilities and characteristics of the mother tongue. Therefore, every course on foreign language is an intercultural cross-cultural communication point. Formation of socio-cultural competence in future English language professionals involves the preparation of a multimedia person.

A secondary worldview of foreign languages and cultures is a scenery that is not just a language-reflective, but language-mediated language. Interactions between primary and secondary world phenomena are a complex psychological process that requires adaptation to another universe without abandoning its "What is it".

Knowledge of the culture of country and language learners at this stage of international communication training is important in using a language. Learning the language with culture is a major aspect of modern linguistic education, not only as deeply ingrained foreign language, but also as a means of influencing a broader socio-cultural relationship between nations of different nations.

Continuous continuity and impartiality of the English language curricula and textbooks for general secondary and secondary special education, as well as issues and authentic texts on the social life style and cultural life of the country's learners, exercises and assignments can be selected on the topic. This ensures that the learning outcomes of the learning outcomes are met by graduates of the socio-cultural competencies listed in the STS (State Training Standard) requirements. However, after graduating from higher education, the existence of a disruption to the chain of interruptions and the incompatibility of higher education curricula with lower education curricula have prevented the gradual evolution of socio-cultural competence.

The survey finds that the personal interest of students in raising the level of communicative competence in a foreign language is related to the following opportunities to enhance their desire to learn a foreign language: Successful professional activity, free communication with other cultural representatives and acquisition of additional information.

Formation of professionally oriented communicative competence of future foreign language students concludes in to interest students in socio-cultural knowledge, activation of existing speech skills and knowledge in their field of culture, interpersonal communication experience; learning and reading through active foreign language information, culturally important information, and the ability to distinguish between national cultures; dividing into stages of the contrastive analysis of values, behavioral models, and communicative culture norms taken in themselves and in foreign cultures.

Teaching equally balanced social and cultural aspects of the country's history, national lifestyle and national tradition is of great importance in developing the socio-cultural competence

of students in the process of English language education, in teaching process. Exercises and assignments may on the subject lead to effective results. Introduction of comprehensively understood information into intercultural collaboration, use of didactic methods such as communicative, interactive, projecting, as well as adherence to aestheticism creates the socio-cultural competence of students since authentic materials are used in authentically social context, and will serve as an effective way to teach the language culture studied.

The new generation of textbooks in the educational process is a set of interactive methods aimed at developing socio-cultural competencies through effective use of electronic textbooks. Concluding the analysis of different explanations of the notion “social-cultural competence” lets conclude that this competence is built on ability to reveal similar and different points between various countries and civilizations, ability to represent native country and its culture.

In this way, the context of professional training of teachers includes ability to interconnect with representatives of foreign culture, ability to interconnect with pupils, as they are also representatives of different cultures though they speak the same language. The result of social-cultural education is formation of social-cultural competence, which leads to successful intercultural communication. Culture and cultural awareness of foreign language country takes place by comparing and evaluating of earlier obtained knowledge and new knowledge in this aspect. Comparison reveals specifics and similarities between different cultures and brings to kind relations and respect to different countries, people and their traditions.

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